

A first record of the Brush-clawed Shore Crab *Hemigrapsus takanoi* for Norfolk

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Nelson aside, some of Norfolk's most famous exports are its crabs. Inhabitants of the globally unique Maastrichtian chalk reef running from Cley to Trimingham, the population of Edible crab *Cancer pagurus* on the north Norfolk coast has supported a fishery for hundreds of years. On 21 October 2022 a new species of crab for the county was recorded for the first time, the Brush-clawed Shore Crab *Hemigrapsus takanoi*. A single female individual was discovered on the exposed rocky shore at West Runton (TG183432; 52.9425, 1.2483; Figs. 1 & 2).

Hemigrapsus takanoi was first described by Asakura and Watanabe (2005). Previously amalgamated with *H. penicillatus* (de Haan 1835), *H. takanoi* was differentiated on male

Figure 1. Location of *Hemigrapsus takanoi* recorded at West Runton, North Norfolk.

Figure 2. Images of *Hemigrapsus takanoi* female recorded at West Runton, North Norfolk. Will Nash.

Figure 3. Male and female *Hemigrapsus takanoi*. **A)** Male, front bottom view showing setal patches and genital plates. **B)** Male, front top view. **C)** Female, front bottom view showing genital plates. **D)** Female, facial detail. *Rudolf Svensen, Stavanger Museum.*

morphology: the presence of larger setal patches and smaller spots of colouration on the front of the animal (Asakura & Watanabe 2005) (Fig. 3A & 3B). The characteristic setal patches may allow males to initiate copulation (Miyajima & Wada 2015).

In the UK, *Hemigrapsus takanoi* can be confused with *H. sanguineus*, although males of this species do not bear setal patches (Asakura & Watanabe 2005). Females can be split based on the morphology of the infraorbital ridge, which in *H. sanguineus* is finely striated and continuous, whereas in *H. takanoi* is more smooth and also divided into three sections (Asakura & Watanabe 2005) (Fig. 3C & 3D).

Hemigrapsus takanoi is a highly invasive species, potentially facilitated by a short life cycle, rapid growth, and early sexual maturity (Gothland *et al.* 2014). It is also able to breed faster in warmer waters (van den Brink *et al.* 2013). Indeed, *H. takanoi* was included in a list of 30 species that were classified as of high risk to native biodiversity in the UK (Roy *et al.* 2014).

Known in European waters since 1994, *Hemigrapsus takanoi* (then under its previous

species name) was initially found in the Bay of Biscay (Noél *et al.* 1997; Gollasch 1998). It is thought to have been introduced from Asian populations via ship hull fouling (Gollasch 1998, Makino *et al.* 2018). *H. takanoi* was also sighted around large ports in the Netherlands (Nijland & Beekman 2000), Belgium (Nuyttens *et al.* 2006), and Germany (Obert *et al.* 2007) during the 2000s, and was well established in France by 2014 (Gothland *et al.* 2014). Following this, the species was recorded from the Baltic Sea (Geburzi *et al.* 2015), and the UK, where it was discovered in the estuaries of the River Colne in Essex and the River Medway in Kent (Wood *et al.* 2015). A large reproductive population was recorded in Suffolk in 2017 (Ashelby *et al.* 2017) (Fig. 4), which can be genetically clustered with crabs from the Baltic and Wadden Seas (Geburzi *et al.* 2020).

So, what of the impact of this new arrival on our native biodiversity? In Dutch waters, where *Hemigrapsus takanoi* has become well established, its occurrence coincides with declines in the European Shore Crab *Carcinus maenas* (van den Brink *et al.* 2012). Along the Atlantic coast of North America,

Figure 4. NBN Atlas records of *Hemigrapsus takanoi*. (<https://species.nbnatlas.org/species/NHM-SYS0001697250>) Accessed 20 November 2022.

the recent arrival of *H. sanguineus*, sister species to *H. takanoi*, has accompanied steep declines in the populations of *C. maenas*. *H. sanguineus* can out-compete *C. maenas* in competition for food (Jensen *et al.* 2002), and also predated its larval instars (Lohrer & Whitlatch 2002), although trends vary between populations (Griffen *et al.* 2011). There is evidence that *H. takanoi* in European waters may reduce recruitment of bivalves and barnacles, but other ecosystem impacts are unclear (Nour *et al.* 2020; Bleile & Thieltges 2021; Cornelius *et al.* 2021). It has been suggested that *H. takanoi* may also vector parasites into European crustacean species (McDermott 2011).

So far, no studies exist on the interaction between *Hemigrapsus takanoi* and the Edible Crab *Cancer pagurus*. Without specific effort in this direction, it remains to be seen if *H. takanoi* will impact the coastal biodiversity of Norfolk and its crab industry. The arrival of such a prolific invasive species highlights

the need for continued recording of change along our coast. Specific training for marine and intertidal species recording is provided by the Seasearch organisation (seasearch.org.uk). Understanding this oft overlooked facet of Norfolk's biodiversity will become increasingly important as the impacts of commercial fishery, shipping, and climate change become ever more evident.

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